

**EVALUATION OF NEUROACTIVE LIGAND RECEPTOR
INTERACTION IN SUBSTANTIA NIGRA PARS COMPACTA
FROM PARKINSON'S BRAIN SAMPLE**

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ABSTRACT

The pathogenesis of Parkinson's disease (PD) includes a broad spectrum of metabolic pathways, from oxidative stress caused by mitochondrial dysfunction, inflammation, abnormal protein metabolism, and aging. Most of these pathophysiological links with PD are the result of studying the functional consequences of gene mutations implicated in familial PD. With the modern genomic technologies numerous genetic risk loci involved in the more frequent non familial form of PD are also being identified, raising new research questions and hopes to better understand and treat this neurodegenerative condition more effectively. Microarray analysis from early studies were collected and systematically analyzed. Different normalization methods were applied to microarray datasets from different platforms. A strategy combining gene co-expression networks and clinical information was adopted, using weighted gene co-expression network analysis (WGCNA) to screen for commonly disturbed genes in different brain regions of patients with PD.

KEYWORDS

Parkinson's Disease, Microarray, Striatum, Normalization, KEGG Pathway

INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease develops when nerve cells, or neurons, are damaged and/or die in an area of the brain that regulates motion. Such neurons usually secrete significant brain chemicals known as dopamine's. When the neurons die or get damaged, they release a smaller amount of dopamine, which causes Parkinson's movement discomfort (1). PD includes tremor, rigidity, bradykinesia, postural instability, gait, festination, dystonia, hypophonia, micrographia and dysphagia. Secondary symptoms are mood, cognitive, sleep, sensational disturbances, weight loss, incontinence and constipation (2).

Currently scientists believe genetic and environmental factors combine in most cases to induce Parkinson's disease. Research on this subject continues vigorously daily. Unfortunately, however, it is usually impossible to determine what caused Parkinson's disease unique to a person (3). While there is effective therapy for

the treatment of the disease-associated bradykinesia, rigidity and tremor, the cause is unknown. The dysregulation of numerous genes in the SN from both PD animal models and human patients has been identified using microarray assays (4). However, the precise roles of the altered gene expressions remain obscure, and the distinct relationships between genes to analyze the collected data using GEO2R to identify significantly expressed genes with various genomic data analyses using Network analyst and to perform pathway analysis utilizing the KEGG Pathway database.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Gene expression profile data GSE20141 was extracted from the Gene Expression Omnibus database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>) (5). The GSE20141 dataset Perform comparative analyses using GEO2R. Adjust microarray analysis settings for accurate interpretation. Analyzing Gene Expression Data. By Incorporating statistical parameters (6). Further Analysis and Data Processing Download full table with gene IDs, p-values, gene symbols, and sequences. Obtain platform file from online portal. Combine series matrix and platform files for necessary data upload. Visualize data using volcano plots, mean difference plots, UMP plots, Venn diagrams, box plots, expression density plots, and a p-value histogram.

GENE INTERACTION OF TF AND PPI

In TF and PPI are comparison of KEGG data, Neuroactive Ligand Receptor Interaction pathway along with chemokine signalling pathway contains 19 significant genes EDN2, GABRP, CHRNA5, HCRT, MCHR2, CGA, CNR2, NMUR1, RXFP2, GRM4, GABRR2, AVPR2, TAAR9, LEP, ADORA2B, MLNR, GCGR, CCL2, CCL21 and CCR4 (7).

Using the Gene Cards (Human gene database) portal, one can explore the functions and publications related to each specific gene implicated in neurodegenerative and Parkinson's disease.

PATHWAY ENRICHMENT

The KEGG PATHWAY database is a collection of manually drawn graphical diagrams, called KEGG pathway maps, for metabolic pathways, signaling pathways, pathways involved in various cellular processes and organismal systems, and

perturbed pathways associated with human diseases, select a pathway from the portal for Homo sapiens, then explore the genes carried within that pathway to search for all genes and understand their relatedness and how one-to-one interactions in cycle form. The function and role of each gene are to be studied and how it is related to Parkinson's disease EDN2, GABRP, CHRNA5, HCRT, MCHR2, CGA, CNR2, NMUR1, RXFP2, GRM4, GABRR2, AVPR2, TAAR9, LEP, ADORA2B, MLNR, GCGR, CCL2,CCL21 and CCR4.

In the context of Parkinson's disease, specific interactions among these genes may contribute to disease pathology. For example, alterations in synaptic protein expression or function (e.g., SV2C, integrins) and disruptions in blood-brain barrier integrity (e.g., laminins, VWF) could influence disease progression.

NETWORK PATHWAYS

In network analysis, in the gene expression table, the enrichment network Visualizes functional categories that are enriched in a network. It carries the KEGG database of ORE type and should play the role of functions the pathways. The pathways are selected and related to AD disease minimum of 5 pathways with genes. It's selected the common gene interacts mostly with all pathways. TNF signaling pathway: Tumor necrosis factor (TNF) is a pro-inflammatory cytokine that plays a role in neuroinflammation, which is implicated in the progression of Parkinson's disease.

KEGG PATHWAY

In the Kegg portal, the cyclic pathway carried Wiring diagrams of molecular interactions, reactions and relations. Select homosapeins organism , it's collection of metabolism, genetic information processing, environmental information processing, cellular processes, organismal systems, human diseases, drug development. how each gene interactions with another gene. Find the related pathway for parkinson's disease. Select the neuroactive ligand interaction (8).

RESULTS

DIFFERENTIAL GENE EXPRESSION AND PATHWAY ENRICHMENT ANALYSIS FOR MICROARRAY DATA

Downloading the series matrix file and platform file on to online portal for the comparison study such as profiling of gene expression and meta-analysis (Network

Analyst). Functions such as quality check and normalization done on to dataset. Quality check is a process used for analysing the quality of dataset such as sample size, experimental factors and adequate gene annotations. Three plots help to study the quality check they are; Box plot, Count sum and Density plot.

BOX PLOT

A graphical standardizing method, arranging numerical data on bases of quartiles. Displaying of data based on five number summaries i.e. first quartile (Q1 minimum), second quartile (Q2 median) and third quartile (Q3 maximum). Generating data results on bases of their symmetry. The quality check box plot shows range of distribution of sample showing raw read counts comparing to control.

Database Normalization is a process done using log2 tool helps for organizing data according to the minimum redundancy from a relation or set of relations, Redundancy in relation may cause insertion, deletion and updation which minimize the redundancy in relations. It is used for elimination or for reducing the redundancy in database tables.

Fig 1: (A) Box plot before normalization; (B) Box plot after normalization

COUNT SUM PLOT

Count sum plot helps in identifying the total read counts of each sample with respect to control. This compare sample value with the control value and give the count sum distribution.

Fig 2: Showing the count sum plot for the sample and the given control. Its obtained before the normalisation of the dataset.

Principle Component Analysis (PCA) PLOT.

PCA analysis is a statistical process which use orthogonal transformation. Its use for checking data quality and to convert the observation of correlated variables into a linear uncorrelated variable. Where, samples are plotted with control for checking its similarities and differences between their visually and help to identify will they group or not.

Fig 3: Showing the PCA plot for the sample and the given control.(A)Before normalisation; (B)after normalisation of the dataset.

Pathways in Kegg -TF gene interaction

EDN2	2.5906
GABRP	2.0478
CHRNA5	2.7459
HCRT	2.0698
MCHR2	2.0997
CGA	2.3351
CNR2	2.5153
NMUR1	2.0718
RXFP2	2.5777
GRM4	2.157
GABRR2	2.0024
AVPR2	2.0019
TAAR9	2.0016
LEP	3.3472
ADORA2B	2.1294
MLNR	2.0073
GCGR	2.4402

Neuroactive ligand receptor interaction have 18 hits in which 17 are up regulated with p value greater than 2.

Pathways in kegg -ppi Gene interactome

Chart Title

CCL2	2.125
CCL21	2.2137
CCR4	2.0612

Chemokine signaling pathway Has 63 hits in which only 3 are up regulated with p value greater than 2.

Box Plot-Genes

Volcano Plot

Showing the VOLCANO plot for the Neuroactive ligand interaction pathway and Chemokine signaling pathway together.

A volcano plot was generated subsequent to normalizing the data with log2 transformation and conducting differential analyses between Parkinson's disease samples and controls. The analysis revealed a significant p-value of 0.5. A total of 5862 genes were identified as significantly downregulated, while 9109 genes were found to be significantly up-regulated.

Heat-Map Clustering.

Heat Map a way of representing data in graphical format such that color-coding helps differentiate the genes. A method used for analysing the sample in combined format with similarities of their gene expression pattern. This help in identifying the gene which are close related to each other in terms of its regulation or biological conditions.

Heat Map Clustering of genes expressed in neuroactive ligand Receptor interaction and Chemokine signaling pathway together.

Analysis Of Pathways In GRN TF Gene Interaction(JASPAR) Within The KEGG Pathway

Transcription factors such as HNF4A, GATA2, RELA, and FOXC1 were found to be significant in the pathway. The genes ADORA2B, LEP, PRKD2, and SMR3B are linked with multiple transcription factors, suggesting they may be involved in diverse biological processes and pathways regulated by these transcription factors.

Analysis Of Pathways in Generic PPI (STRING Interactome) Within The KEGG Pathway

The chemokine signaling pathway analysis reveals LCK's central role, with CCL2 and GRB7 showing regulatory links to LCK via RELA, CXCR4, and direct interaction, respectively. Additionally, CCL5's connection to CCR4 underscores intricate interactions. Overall, the pathway exhibits a complex network with potential crosstalk between signaling molecules.

KEGG PATHWAY ENRICHMENT ANALYSIS

Pathway enrichment analysis identified connections between various pathways, including NAFLD, Parkinson's disease, cardiac muscle contraction, Alzheimer's disease, Huntington's disease, and oxidative phosphorylation. The genes COX6C and COX412 were found to be instrumental in establishing links among all these pathways.

DISCUSSION

The neuroactive ligand interaction pathway, as analyzed using the KEGG database, implicates various genes such as EDN2, GABRP, CHRNA5, HCRT, MCHR2, CGA, CNR2, NMUR1, RXFP2, GRM4, GABRR2, AVPR2, TAAR9, LEP, ADORA2B, MLNR, and GCGR. Among these, several key genes stand out:

Endothelin (EDN2): Regulates vascular tone; elevated levels linked to hypertension and inflammation, exacerbating Parkinson's disease (PD). Orexin (HCRT): Essential for sleep regulation; dysfunction causes narcolepsy with cataplexy. Anandamide (ADORA2B): Modulates neurotransmitter release; upregulation in PD suggests compensatory response to dopamine depletion. Leptin (LEP): Implicated in neuroinflammation and neuroprotection; associated with multiple sclerosis and PD, influencing neuronal structure and plasticity. Adenosine (ADORA2B): Inhibits neuronal activity, impacting sleep, learning, and memory; potential therapeutic role in PD due to cognitive effects.

CONCLUSION

The identification of specific genes within these pathways, including EDN2, HCRT, ADORA2B, CHRNA5, NMUR1, LEP, and others, underscores their potential significance in PD pathogenesis. These genes, with their diverse functions spanning neurotransmission, inflammation, and neuronal plasticity, offer promising avenues for further exploration and therapeutic intervention in PD and related neurodegenerative disorders.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Author has no conflict of interest

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